

Collecting and Displaying the Decommissioning of North Sea Oil and Gas at National Museums Scotland

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National Museums Scotland (NMS) has a long history of collecting industrial objects. Our predecessor museum, the Industrial Museum of Scotland, was founded with the intention of collecting the materials and processes of manufacture. That is, contemporary technologies and the tacit skills that went with them (Alberti et al. 2018). For a lot of the museum's lifetime the emphasis has tended to be more on historical collecting but there has always been a remit for collecting relevant current material. In recent years, this has been distilled and formalised into a strategic priority within our Collections Development Strategy.

In terms of our energy collections this means that we aim to build on our world-class collections and expertise in the areas of energy generation and consumption, working with industry and universities to collect innovative technology and industrial material as its working life concludes (National Museums Scotland 2017).

This collecting target aligns closely with the acquisition of material from transforming industries. This includes the nuclear industry, the oil and gas industry and the renewable energy sector.

Contemporary collecting and decommissioning – looking back and forward

A key acquisition from recent years is the flare tip from the Murchison oil platform. Although this is a piece of contemporary collecting, it in many ways represents the end of a technical endeavour, rather than the beginning (Alberti et al. 2018). That said, the decommissioning of Scotland's oil and gas industry is an industry in itself. It will take approximately 25-35 years to dismantle nearly 500 offshore installations and looks set to cost between £45 billion and £77 billion (House of Commons Committee of Public Accounts 2019). So, collecting the flare tip from the Murchison oil platform is a way of looking back at the recent past and also of representing the beginning of a new and significant chapter. The item itself has just entered the realm of obsolescence, but the process of retrieving it and dismantling the platform, where it operated from 1982 until 2014, is a new, expanding and evolving discipline that is going to be relevant for decades to come as is reflected in the fact that the University of Aberdeen now offering a master's degree in decommissioning.

The Significance of NS O&G and how it is already represented in our collections

North Sea Oil has been vital to Scotland and Britain for more than half a century. The first licenses to drill were granted in 1964. Since then, thousands have been employed in the industry and it has generated vast income for the government and private companies alike. We have become reliant on oil and gas products for fuel for transport, manufacture of plastics and cleaning products and gas for heating. In its peak year of production, the Brent oil field supplied enough energy to meet the annual needs of half of the UK's homes (Jack 2017). The industry has been central to UK politics as well, playing a prominent role in the Scottish independence debate and has been used to make various arguments during the Brexit discussion, from the impact that the loss of access to markets and EU workers may have on the industry (Symon 2018), to whether it would provide the economic buffer needed in the event of a hard or no deal Brexit (Critchlow 2018).

Oil and gas have been, and continue to be, central to our economy and politics and have provided employment to an enormous workforce both off and on shore, with up to 200 people working on an

oil rig on one shift and a vast support and supply industry of goods, services and cargo vessels based on the mainland to provide safety cover and maintain the cities in the sea (Cox and Taubman, 2017). In 2014, the website Scotjobsnet.co.uk said, “It is difficult to put an exact figure on how many jobs oil and gas supports in the Aberdeen area, although 23,500 people, equivalent to 10.3% of the workforce, are employed directly by the industry. It has been estimated that a further 82,000 people work locally in the supply chain, which would mean the sector accounted for 46% of jobs in the area” (Scotjobsnet 2014).

The developments in the industry since the 1960s were already well represented in the NMS collections by drill and platform models used to inform manufacture, samples of North Sea oil, a cross section of the Ninian oil pipeline from Sullom Voe terminal in Shetland, which is on display alongside drill bits and a model of the Elgin wellhead in the Scotland: A Changing Nation gallery in the Museum of Scotland.

These collections form a powerful core of the Science and Technology collections and enhance our ability to tell the story of 20th and 21st century Scotland. In order to continue to tell that story we needed to collect the beginning of the decommissioning story and that is where our relationship with the Murchison platform began.

Murchison

The Murchison oil platform is located 240 kilometres north east of Shetland. The platform was installed in 1979 and began producing oil in 1980. It produced more than 390 million barrels of oil before its shutdown in 2014. One of the largest North Sea oil platforms ever built, the huge structure has been described as scaled up Gothic cathedral in the sea (Cox and Taubman 2017). Murchison was part of the first wave of North Sea decommissioning so in many ways embodied what was to come in the industry over the following decades.

It was a perfect collecting target for NMS which wanted to develop its collection on three levels: the decline of the industry; the engineering involved in removing these mega-structures from the North Sea and – perhaps most importantly – the people who work in these alien environments (Cox 2016).

The first challenge in collecting of this nature is how to reach out to the companies involved, start to build a relationship where political sensitivities and concerns about reputational risk could contribute to resistance and build a case for why elements of their work should be collected for heritage purposes. NMS was incredibly lucky to have a “way in” to Canadian Natural Resources, the owners and operators of the Murchison platform, through the visual artist Sue Jane Taylor. Sue Jane has a deep understanding of the energy industries, workforce and environments having spent more than 30 years recording people and their technologies (Cox and Taubman 2017). She has gained access to remote and publicly prohibited offshore installations, and had been invited by Canadian Natural Resources to make three visits to Murchison between 2014 and 2016. NMS had the good fortune to have worked with Sue Jane back in 2008 when developing the gallery called Scotland: A Changing Nation, which uses some of her sketchbooks and etchings from her earlier work to contextualise the interpretation of the offshore industries. She, therefore, was able to NMS staff at the time in touch with the right people at Canadian Natural Resources. Sue has continued to be a good friend to NMS and indeed went on to work with us further on an exhibition called Age of Oil in 2017.

The opportunity provided by this existing relationship along with the significance of Murchison as an early decommissioning project made it the obvious candidate to try and collect from. The first phase of this collection was very much with the development of the new science and technology galleries

in the National Museum of Scotland in mind. Among these galleries, which opened in 2016, is “Energise” which explores the evolution and issues surrounding the different types of energy in Scotland’s portfolio, from fossil fuels to nuclear to cutting edge renewables. At that stage NMS collected a sample of the last crude oil to come off Murchison, the driller’s console and telephone that were used on the platform for more than 35 years to control the drilling of 98 wells and two pipeline pigs, designed to clean debris from oil pipes and named for the squealing noise they make in the process. One of the pigs and the console are on display in Energise, and the other pig, the telephone and the oil have been displayed as part of the Age of Oil exhibition. Another wonderful thing about the relationship with Sue Jane Taylor and her work and contacts in the industry and with the Murchison staff was that she was able to source oral history recordings and film footage that supported the interpretation of these items, both in the permanent gallery and temporary exhibition, and will become part of the permanent history files for these objects (Alberti et al. 2018).

Flare Tip

While these objects all tell parts of the story of the oil industry and its decommissioning, it was the slightly later and much larger acquisition of the Murchison platform flare tip that is probably the most impressive and most powerful symbol of the technical, human and decommissioning stories. An oil rig is probably the most recognisable icon of the industry, but collecting an entire rig would be problematic and beyond the capacity of NMS. The flare tip was selected as an emblem of the whole rig, a part to represent the whole. At over four metres tall and weighing a ton, the flare tip is probably NMS’s biggest acquisition of recent years, outside of the aviation collections. NMS felt that flare tip would provide a powerful experience of the scale of the industry and of the interface between humanity and industry.

Sue Jane Taylor’s footage of life on Murchison and her oral history interviews provide a real sense of human interaction with technology through the flare tip. A worker must climb 259 steps to inspect the tip, with the ocean churning below. The hair-raising piece of film showing this emphasises the riskier side of offshore work and the challenging environment the workers had to face every day to do their jobs.

Extinguishing the flare tip was highly symbolic and represented the end of the working life of this massive structure. This made the flare tip an even more pertinent object to collect to symbolise the beginning of the decommissioning process.

It was hoped that the flare tip would be a prompt to start discussions among NMS’s visitors around our reliance on fossil fuels and what this means for the future. That it would raise questions about energy security, dependence on petroleum related products, Government climate change targets, and loss of income from the industry as it declines. It could also spark debate about what to do with the infrastructure of industry when it becomes obsolete or no longer functional. What should be done with the almost 500 platforms and the 10,000km (Jack 2017) of steel pipeline that will need to be removed from the North Sea over the coming decades? What about the suggestion that the underwater parts of oil rigs could simply be cleaned up and left in the ocean to become marine habitats? Is that viable? Is it environmental? Given that the Murchison flare tip is the only one that has been saved for heritage reasons, what has happened, or will happen, to the all the others?

On that last point, the “proposal for acquisition” that was prepared to make the case to acquire the flare tip says: “No other Museum in the UK holds a flare tip in their collection - we would be the first to do so. It will be as significant a legacy for our successors as the Boulton-Watt engine was for us. It

will be a unique synecdoche for the rig as a whole; and therefore decommissioning, and therefore North Sea oil; and therefore the Scottish experience in the twenty-first century.”

Challenges of Collection

The challenges of collecting large industrial objects from remote and hostile environments are plentiful and various, ranging from how to physically access and move the items, to the potentially huge costs involved

Again, the good relationship with Canadian Natural Resources was absolutely crucial in addressing these challenges. Most of the Murchison structure was being shipped to Norway to be scrapped. Canadian Natural Resources were extremely generous in agreeing to have the flare tip brought to a scrapyards in the north of Scotland, which is where staff from NMS first got to go and see it. There is no way that this could have happened without assistance from Canadian Natural Resources who removed it from the oil platform and brought it to the mainland at their own expense, and who also prepared it for onward transport to Edinburgh. Not only did they cover these costs and time, but they sacrificed the not inconsiderable scrap value of this nickel-chromium based superalloy. Without the relationship nurtured by Sue Jane Taylor and then NMS staff during the earlier phase of collecting, it is hard to imagine this having happened. We were also very fortunate to have the assistance of Canadian Natural Resources Decommissioning Projects Manager, Roy Aspden. Mr Aspden clearly had a good understanding of the importance of preserving elements of the industry for heritage purposes. He said that he had been inspired by a visit to Stavanger where remnants of decommissioned oil platforms have been incorporated into the city's physical infrastructure, such as the Geopark which is built on and abandoned oil platform and whose landscape is based on the geological layers of the oil field.

Challenges of Display

Since arriving at the National Museums Collections Centre in Granton, Edinburgh, the flare tip has been accessible to visitors both on monthly public tours and also by appointment for anyone. It does not currently have any interpretation with it, but all of the rich materials generated and collected by Sue Jane Taylor are available. Recently, some of her images and diary extracts were incorporated into a tour to emphasise the human endeavour that the flare tip represents. It would be ideal to show her film of the man climbing the steps as part of the tour because that footage so stunningly illustrates all the elements that the object brings together, but how to show it as part of a tour in a storage area is not obvious, although carrying a tablet with the film clip on it would be one solution.

However, I think that this demonstrates that, for audiences to fully experience and appreciate the flare tip, seeing it in store is not ideal. Indeed, a visitor on a recent tour asked when it was going to be on display somewhere more public. He was generally taken aback by the sheer volume of our collections in storage and was asking the same question about many of the things that he saw that day. While it is the kind of question that can make our hearts sink in museums, it is a perfectly reasonable question from someone who is not familiar with how we work as institutions and who knows that our funding often comes from the public purse.

Among the staff at NMS there is fondness and enthusiasm for the flare tip as well as belief in its value as a piece of heritage and a way of communicating with audiences. However, its size present real challenges for us in terms of displaying it in one of our more publicly accessible spaces.

Earlier this year, we received word that the director of NMS, had been walking around the stores in the Collection Centre and his eye fell up on the flare tip and he enquired as to why it was not on

display. Since then, staff have made new efforts to explore ways of doing this. There are different groups within the organisation who have different stakes in significant changes to displays and who have different priorities and work schedules, so it may take some time to complete this piece of work.

Potential locations where the flare tip could be displayed have been identified and now the greater challenges of how to bring it into the building and how to display it safely still need to be addressed. Then there is the challenge of prioritising this work amongst all the other work that our multi-disciplinary museum is currently engaged with. However, in the near future we intend to properly share this object with our audiences as the oil and gas industry and its decommissioning continues to play a central role in Scottish life, albeit a shifting role in an ever-changing social, political and economic environment.

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